

Synthesis and analytical applications of a new chelating resin containing diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid

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A new chelating resin based on a phenol-formaldehyde copolymer containing diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) as a functional species has been synthesized. Capacity and sorption kinetics have been studied. The complexation ability (distribution coefficients) of the sorbent towards 19 metal ions has been studied. The resin may successfully be applied to the selective separation and recovery of some metal ions.

The need for more specific, metal ion separation and recovery process in both hydrometallurgical and analytical applications has led to an increasing interest in chelating ion exchangers. In particular, the search for 'ion-specific' resins, which under proper operating conditions, are selective for only one ionic species¹ has been intensified. The chemistry underlying the use of ion-exchange and chelating polymers for the separation and preconcentration of trace metal ions is reasonably well understood².

A review concerned with the application of chelating polymeric resin for the separation and preconcentration of trace metals has been reported³. A new chelating sorbent based on pyrazolone containing amines immobilized on styrenedivinylbenzene copolymer has been reported⁴ to be selective for Au^{III}, Pd^{II}, and Ag^I. The preparation and properties of chelating resins containing 1-nitroso-2-naphthol⁵ have been reported. This communication describes the synthesis and metal-ion uptake experiments of a novel In^{III}- and Th^{IV}-selective hydrophilic ion exchange resin based on phenol-formaldehyde with diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid as a chelating ligand (PF-DTPA) (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

The content of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (12.85%) in the chelating resin was found by determining nitrogen content of the sorbent and comparing it with that

Scheme 1

of initial DTPA. The IR spectra of the initial DTPA and chelating resin revealed at 1620 (C=O), 1091/1360 (C-N) and 1209 cm⁻¹ (C-O). Comparison of the characteristic bands signifies that the chelating groups are present in the resin.

The results of sorption capacity for Ag^I, Co^{II}, Pb^{II}, Al^{III}, La^{III}, In^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, and Th^{IV} are shown in Table 1. The maximum capacity was found for Th^{IV}.

The resins were heated at temperature (40–80°) in a hot air-oven for 1 h and cooled to room temperature. The sorption capacities for Th^{IV} at pH 6 were 431.6, 431.2, 430.0, 428.4 and 360.4 mg g⁻¹ at 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80°, respectively. The capacity loss above 70° seems due to distortion

Table 1. The sorption capacity (mg/g) of the phenol-formaldehyde-DTPA resin for metal ions

pH	Ag ^I	Co ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	Al ^{III}	La ^{III}	In ^{III}	Pt ^{IV}	Zr ^{IV}	Th ^{IV}
2	76.23	10.61	41.44	4.85	55.56	138.93	170.50	100.34	380.54
4	76.55	16.50	45.58	6.24	63.90	182.56	201.33	120.06	408.37
6	88.44	22.40	58.01	9.17	103.89	200.93	216.93	133.18	431.57

Table 2. K_d Values of metal on phenol-formaldehyde-DTPA resin

Metal ion	DMW	pH 2	pH 4	pH 6	0.1 M NaNO ₃
Zn ^{II}	40.0	4.1	8.6	37.0	10.5
Cd ^{II}	122.7	12.4	21.5	61.2	102.6
Hg ^{II}	55.0	34.8	44.4	100.0	106.3
Cu ^{II}	73.0	14.4	18.8	45.0	28.6
Ag ^{II}	416.4	218.6	220.0	315.6	368.4
Co ^{II}	128.0	40.0	65.9	95.0	102.6
Ni ^{II}	102.6	31.8	36.2	55.8	61.2
Mg ^{II}	30.9	12.2	18.4	21.3	2.0
Ca ^{II}	40.4	16.4	24.8	30.7	4.0
Ba ^{II}	121.5	41.8	50.4	58.7	16.4
Mn ^{II}	105.0	25.0	29.4	74.0	30.6
Fe ^{III}	209.0	48.9	69.8	05.0	80.4
Al ^{III}	92.7	35.0	46.9	81.2	50.2
In ^{III}	3162.4	605.0	1514.0	2692.0	2976.4
Zr ^{IV}	1504.0	488.0	850.0	1081.5	1432.4
Th ^{IV}	T.A.	2050.0	3520.0	7440.0	3520.0
Pt ^{IV}	560.4	310.2	426.8	500.0	-
Pb ^{II}	171.4	44.4	49.4	65.1	58.7
La ^{III}	266.6	100.0	119.5	238.0	277.0

Table 3. Separation achieved on chelating resin columns

Sl no.	Mixture	Eluent	Eluate ml	Amount loaded μg	Amount found μg	Error %
1.	Zn ^{II}	0.1M NaNO ₃	30	327	329	+0.61
	Hg ^{II}	0.1M HNO ₃	40	400	397	-0.75
2.	Cu ^{II}	0.1M HNO ₃	30	318	320	+0.63
	Ag ^{II}	1M NH ₃	40	215	212	-1.41
3.	Mg ^{II}	DMW	30	243	243	0.00
	Ba ^{II}	0.1M NaNO ₃	30	274	273	-0.36
4.	Cd ^{II}	0.1M HNO ₃	30	225	227	+0.88
	Zr ^{IV}	1M HNO ₃	40	364	360	-1.09
5.	La ^{III}	0.2M HNO ₃	30	270	272	+0.74
	Th ^{IV}	1M HNO ₃	50	464	458	-1.29
6.	Zn ^{II}	0.1M NaNO ₃	30	327	328	+0.30
	Pb ^{II}	0.1M HNO ₃	40	410	412	+0.48
7.	Al ^{III}	0.01M HNO ₃	30	270	271	+0.37
	Th ^{IV}	0.1M HNO ₃	50	464	460	-0.86
8.	Al ^{III}	0.01M HNO ₃	30	270	272	+0.74
	La ^{III}	0.2M HNO ₃	30	270	268	-0.74
	In ^{III}	0.1M HNO ₃	40	230	227	-1.30
9.	Zn ^{II}	0.1M NaNO ₃	30	327	329	+0.61
	Fe ^{III}	0.1M HNO ₃	30	558	562	+0.71
	In ^{III}	1M HNO ₃	50	230	226	-1.73

of the resin matrix.

Kinetic study : The kinetic study for the adsorption of Zr^{IV} on chelating resin was carried out at optimum pH conditions. To analyze the kinetic data we applied Vermeulen's approximation⁶ expressed in the equation,

$$\ln(1-F^2) = -kt$$

where, $F = [M]_t / [M]_{eq}$ and k is the experimentally observed rate constants, $[M]_t$ and $[M]_{eq}$ denote the Zr^{IV} concentrations retained in the resin (mmol g⁻¹) at time t and at equilibrium, respectively. A linear relationship between $\ln(1-F^2)$ and time indicates that the kinetic equation adopted is valid in this system. The rate-determining step appears to be particle-diffusion process. The rate constant at pH 6 was determined as $7.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ by least-squares method. Therefore, the half-life under the present conditions is approximately 16 min.

Distribution studies : Distribution coefficients (K_d values) of 19 metal ions in demineralized water (DMW), 0.1M NaNO₃ and buffer solutions (pHs 2, 4 and 6) are presented in Table 2. The K_d values decreased with decreasing pH and in 0.1M NaNO₃. The reason for selective sorption and desorption of the metal ions at certain pH can be attributed to large difference in stability constants of metal-amine complexes. The resin also behaves as a weak cation exchanger (ion exchange capacity = 0.12 meq g⁻¹ resin for Na⁺/H⁺). The decrease in K_d values in 0.1 M NaNO₃ may be attributed due to Na⁺ as competing cation.

In general, the separation factors, $K_d(M)/K_d(M^*)$, for two metal ions M and M* for which $K_d(M) > K_d(M^*)$, increased with increasing acid concentration (lower pH). It is therefore, important to optimize the acid concentration in order to obtain the best separations and to elute metal ions with the minimum volume of eluent.

Separations : On the basis of large difference in K_d values separations were tried and experimentally successful results are reported in Table 3. It is interesting to note that no significant tailing was obtained during the elution of various metal ions and only small volume of eluents were required to give compact chromatograms.

Recovery of Th^{IV} and In^{III} and effect of foreign ions : The results of recovery In^{III} and Th^{IV} (Table 4) reveal that recoveries are quantitative. The study of tolerance limits for various ions in the recovery of In^{III} and Th^{IV} from water samples reveals that cations (Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II} and Ca^{II}) and anions (Cl⁻, Br⁻ and SO₄²⁻) in the concentration ranges 100–400 and 100–800 mg dm⁻³, respectively, had almost no interference.

Table 4. Recovery of In^{III} and Th^{IV} from 1000 ml of water samples

Sample	Added, μg		Recovered, μg			
	In ^{III}	Th ^{IV}	In ^{III}	R S D *	Th ^{IV}	R S D *
				%		%
Distilled water	344	464	345	0.41	460	0.45
Tap water	344	464	342	0.43	462	0.47
	688	928	638	0.46	923	0.50
Synthetic	344	464	346	0.55	461	0.58
Sea water	688	928	693	0.60	924	0.62

*R S D = Relative standard deviation

Experimental

A Systronic 335 pH meter and Shimadzu 8201 PC were used for pH measurement and FTIR spectra (KBr), respectively. Nitrogen was determined using a Heraeus-Carlo-Erba 1108 analyzer. Diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (Fluka), phenol and formaldehyde solution (B.D.H.,) were used. All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

The resin was synthesized by mixing phenol (0.1 mol), formaldehyde (0.2 mol) and DTPA (0.01 mol) in presence of 2 M H₂SO₄ (50 ml) as catalyst. The mixture was heated at 60–70° in a water-bath with stirring for 6 h. The separated resinous product was washed with DMW, dried at 60° in a vacuum oven, ground and sieved to 60–100 mesh.

Distribution coefficients : Portion of dry resin (0.05 g) were equilibrated for 6 h in a mechanical shaker at 25±1° with 20 ml solution containing 0.1 mmol of the metal ions and NaOAc-HOAc or NaCl-HCl buffer solutions or NaNO₃ solution as shown in Table 1. After equilibration the resin was separated by filtration. The filtrate was analyzed for metal ions by EDTA titrations⁷ except Pt^{IV} and Ag^I. Pt^{IV} with potassium iodide and Ag^I with dithiazone were determined spectrophotometrically⁸. The distribution coefficients (K_d values) were calculated from the following equation

$$K_d (\text{ml g}^{-1}) = \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion in resin g}^{-1}}{\text{Amount of metal ion in solution ml}^{-1}}$$

Capacity studies : The resin (0.05 g) was shaken with an aqueous solution (20 ml) having metal ion (0.2 mmol) (pHs 2, 4 and 6). After the distribution equilibrium had been reached, the concentration of the metal ion in solution was determined.

Kinetic study : The resin (2 g) was stirred with aqueous solution (200 ml) (pH 6) containing 0.012 M of Zr^{IV}. The reaction temperature was maintained at 25° in a thermostated water-bath. While stirring at a speed of 80 rpm, a small portion of the solution was withdrawn at appropriate intervals and the concentration of Zr^{IV} was determined by EDTA

titration. The kinetic data were analyzed by Vermeulens's approximation⁶.

Separations Borosilicate glass tube (5 mm i.d. × 200 mm) joined to a wider upper part (15 mm i.d. × 100 mm) served as the column. The column was filled with a slurry of resin (2 g), washed with DMW (50 ml) and then the mixture of ions having concentrations 0.517–1.115 mg/10 ml was introduced into the column and allowed to be sorbed. The metal ions were then eluted separately using suitable eluting reagents and determined by EDTA titration. The flow rate was maintained at about 0.2 ml min⁻¹ throughout the column process.

Recovery from tap water and sea water : Tap water and synthetic sea water⁹ (1000 ml each, pH ~2) were filtered and spiked with In^{III} (344 and 688 μg) and Th^{IV} (464 and 928 μg), respectively. The water samples were passed through the column packed with the resin (2 g) at the flow rate 4–5 ml min⁻¹. The adsorbed In^{III} or Th^{IV} was eluted using 1 M HNO₃ (~50 ml) and analyzed by EDTA titration.

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